

SOLUTIONS TO GROUNDWATER SCARCITY

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Abstract

Groundwater remains one of the most dependable sources of freshwater for households, agriculture, and industry. However, growing scarcity has raised concerns about its long-term availability and quality. This paper examines the drivers and consequences of groundwater depletion and explores practical approaches for sustaining this resource. Drawing on recent studies and reports, the review identifies how poor management, population growth, and climate variability have placed increasing pressure on aquifers, making them less reliable for potable and domestic use. The discussion highlights four key areas for tackling scarcity: strengthening groundwater sustainability practices, implementing effective monitoring systems, applying advanced technical methods, and supporting evidence-based decision-making. By integrating these approaches, the study emphasizes that groundwater resources can be managed more effectively to meet present needs while safeguarding future supply.

1.0 Introduction

One of humanity's fundamental requirements is water, and changes in water resources directly affect society (Besada and Werner, 2015). Water can't be underestimated and underrated as it's

part of life as almost everything on planet Earth is sustained by water. For development to be sustainable, the various products produced by man are being made with water in its minute or large quantity, and as such water can be termed "life" Water is required. Consequently, the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs: 6) as guaranteeing water security for all (Zhao and Varis, 2021). Surface water and groundwater, make up around 2% and 98% of the total freshwater that is now available on Earth in the form of liquid, respectively (Margat and van, 2013). 35% of the total amount of water used for human use worldwide comes from groundwater. According to Döll et al. (2012), groundwater contributes 42%, 36%, and 27% of the total water used for irrigation, home consumption, and industrial use.

The existence of humans depends on groundwater since it is used by people all over the world for a variety of purposes, including domestic consumption, irrigation, and industrial use. In addition to making up around 0.76% of the world's total water, which includes oceans and ice sheets, groundwater accounts for about 30% of the freshwater supply on Earth, and thereby could be considered a life supporter to humans. Groundwater is replenished from the surface, where it can also naturally flow as springs and seeps and create wetland oases.

Hydrogeology, often known as groundwater hydrology, is the study of how groundwater is distributed and moves, this study of water, helps to elaborate the essence of groundwater, flow, and source. To a layman, water is heard to be stored underground, his assumption of groundwater could be seen at a basic level, but to every hydrogeologist, there is a geology, physics, and chemistry to the existence of groundwater at a particular depth.

When compared to surface water, groundwater is frequently less expensive, more practical, and less prone to pollution. It is therefore frequently utilized for public water supply. For instance, due to the enormous volume of water that is stored underground in aquifers, groundwater serves as Nigeria's main source of usable water storage and enables the construction of larger reservoirs. Around a million people worldwide rely only on groundwater as their primary water source, and many municipal water sources are drawn from it, to sustain the large number of people living and existing in the municipal area.

Also, 1.2 billion people lack access to inexpensive, safe home-giving water and safe water for home consumption (WHO, 2003). Less widely known is the fact that a substantial portion of the 900 million people living in rural areas and making less than \$1 per day do not have access to water for their daily needs, the access to this water seems too greyly as no good road to access good and portal water at their far distance.

The well-being of humans is significantly impacted by access to water, sometimes, when sick men, women, or infants are identified, then the findings would be justified by the scarcity of good water. Poor personal hygiene and a lack of access to safe drinking water and sanitation have a significant negative impact on health, especially diarrheal diseases, which are estimated to claim the lives of 2.18 million people each year, with 75 percent of them being children under the age of five, and result in 82 million disability-adjusted life years worldwide (Prüss et al., 2002). Lack of access to water for productive uses has a disproportionately negative impact on the world's poorest people, creating a cycle of starvation, poverty, and disease. A variety of global issues, including

health, malnutrition, poverty, and the sustainable use of natural resources, depend on clean water.

1.1 What is Groundwater scarcity?

Groundwater is the shortage of water, a conflict between supply and demand. Both the amount and quality of groundwater resources may be impacted. Lack of groundwater can increase the danger of waterborne infections, reduce access to clean water for drinking and hygiene, and raise the price of water. In relative terms, groundwater scarcity depends on supply and demand factors.

The lack of water availability "due to physical shortage or scarcity in access due to the failure of institutions to assure a regular supply or a lack of suitable infrastructure," as defined by the United Nations (UN-Water, 2021), is referred to as water scarcity. Local ecology and arid conditions, as well as bad management and infrastructure, can all contribute to water scarcity. A 2016 study from the Netherlands' Twente Water Centre stated that four billion people experience "severe water scarcity at least 1 month of the year." According to a group of academics led by Peter Burek of the International Institute for Applied Systems Analysis in Austria, as many as 4.8 billion to 5.7 billion people may experience severe water scarcity by the year 2050. We refer to people as being water insecure if they lack access to safe, inexpensive water to meet their needs for drinking, washing, or sustaining their livelihood.

A very complex resource is water. In contrast to a static resource like land, water happens in a very dynamic cycle of precipitation, runoff, and evaporation, with huge temporal and spatial variations as well as quality variations that entirely determine its worth to people and ecosystems. Water can be a problem (in floods) or a life-saving resource (in droughts), but it is more shocking that both situations might exist in the same area within a single year. A situation

like this makes it difficult to quantify water scarcity using annual average water availability.

The metrics of water shortage are also impacted by spatial scales. It goes without saying that in very vast nations like China, there may be a water shortage in the Yellow River basin and flooding in the Yangtze River basin at the same time. Across far lower spatial scales, the same phenomenon also occurs in many smaller nations. Another important factor in determining how scarce water is should be water quality. Fresh water may become contaminated as it moves downstream and end up being useless. Do we count contaminated water as a resource that can be used to meet demands (after treatment)? Or do you just ignore it and assume there is a scarcity? The response would be that contaminated water would be a scarcity but, in contrast, this contaminated water can be a resource and helpful to man when treated to meet the demands of the people especially in arid regions in the world.

Where surface water is scarce, dependence on groundwater is greater; notable examples include hyper and dry regions that rely heavily on groundwater supplies to support human activity (Bhakar and Singh, 2018; Rijsberman, 2006). The main causes of the over-exploitation of groundwater that might result in the depletion of groundwater resources include changes in land use, rapid growth in socioeconomic conditions in society, and climate (Foster et al., 2017). Groundwater quality degradation is an increasing concern in addition to excessive groundwater use (Haritash et al., 2016). The following explanations illustrate how issues with groundwater scarcity, and stress may result from the depletion and quality degradation of groundwater supplies.

2.0 Causes of Groundwater Scarcity

The causes of groundwater scarcity are the following items.

1. Water Pollution
2. Agriculture
3. Population Growth
4. Climate Change

2.1 Water Pollution

One of the main factors contributing to water scarcity is water contamination. Water contamination can be caused by chemicals, oil, industrial waste, faeces, pesticides, and fertilizers. They may have an immediate impact or gradually accumulate over many years in the environment. Moreover, these contaminants have the potential to contaminate subsurface aquifers.

Fig 1. Water Pollution

According to research, between 700 million and 1.36 billion people are thought to be impacted by water pollution directly or indirectly, according to senior author Ting Ma of the Chinese Academy of Sciences essay published in the journal Nature in January 2020. The Niger River Delta in and around Port Harcourt, Nigeria, is

one of the most severely impacted areas of the world by water pollution. An ecological catastrophe has been caused by hundreds of oil spills each year, natural gas flaring, and illegal crude oil refining, which release hazardous compounds into the environment. There is a need for "immediate actions to improve the quality of drinking water for the residents of the Niger Delta," according to experts at the University of Port Harcourt.

Another country with significant issues with water pollution and water scarcity is India. Almost every sort of water pollution in the Ganges River includes present in the Ganges River, including untreated sewage discharge, gray water from residential and commercial structures, agricultural runoff, industrial waste, animal corpses, and partially or completely burned carcasses during funeral ceremonies. Waterways in Jakarta, Indonesia, and the Nile River in Egypt are two other places with significant pollution issues.

A peer-reviewed interdisciplinary publication called *Chemical Perspectives* claims that leachate is created as landfill material breaks down and rain washes the end products away. It states that leachate poses a serious health danger because the dark liquid is full of microorganisms that can contaminate groundwater as well as organic and inorganic compounds and heavy metals.

Similarly to this, leachate has negative effects on the ecosystem due to its high concentration of metals and dangerous compounds, according to (Rana *et al.*, 2018). According to the report, leachate typically has significant concentrations of ammonia, nitrogen, and heavy metals as well as a bright color and unpleasant odour. **2.2 Agricultural Uses of Water**

Water usage for agriculture is a significant cause of water scarcity, particularly in nations with extensive food production like India, China, Australia, Spain, and the United States. "Groundwater depletion due to intensive withdrawals for agriculture is becoming an issue of increasing concern in certain areas, where it threatens to undermine food security, basic water supply, climate resilience, and the environmental integrity of groundwaterdependent wetlands and watercourses," the UN World Water Development Report 2022 states.

In rural areas, agriculture is the main source of groundwater pollution, and it is thought that globally, agricultural pollution has surpassed contamination from habitations and businesses.

The most common anthropogenic contaminant in groundwater worldwide is nitrate, which is produced by chemical and organic fertilizers and contributes to the eutrophication of surface waters. When used incorrectly or disposed of, insecticides, herbicides, and fungicides can potentially contaminate groundwater with carcinogens and other harmful compounds.

Both a major contributors to and a victim of water scarcity, and agriculture. Almost 70% of all water withdrawals are used for agriculture, and in some developing nations, this percentage might reach 95%. As time goes on, we will need to use our natural resources more carefully, and water is no exception. For instance, the type of crop chosen has a significant impact on the amount of water required. Did you know that pulse crops have a modest water footprint, requiring only 125 liters of water to produce 1 kg of lentils? In contrast, 1 kg of beef requires 13,000 liters of water to create. **2.3 Population Growth Effects on Water** The FAO, year claims that the amount of water use has reached unsustainable heights because of population

growth, associated economic development, industrialization, and changing eating trends. As nations develop, there is a dramatic increase in demand for more goods, housing, and water-intensive agriculture, which puts more strain on the water supply. According to the FAO, during the preceding century, the rate at which the world's population increased was more than doubled. According to projections, by 2050, the world's population will need 200 million tons more of beef and one billion more tons of cereal annually. According to the Beef Cattle Research Council, one kilogram of beef requires close to 16,000 liters of water.

The nations with the fastest population increase will likely have the worst water scarcity issues. Population growth projections from the World Bank and estimates of the number of people who would experience water scarcity in 2050 from a 2021 Nature article imply that the relationship between population growth and water scarcity will remain positive.

2.4 Climate Change Effects on Water "Water is the key medium through which we will feel the effects of climate change," according to UN-WATER, 2020. According to research from the Columbia Climate School, plants will probably grow bigger, and their growing seasons will be longer as atmospheric carbon dioxide levels rise. As a result, more water would be retained over time, potentially limiting the amount of moisture on the ground. The distribution of precipitation will be substantially altered by climate change. While the Southwest, southern Great Plains, and Southeast may endure lengthier droughts in the United States, the Midwest is predicted to get wetter. According to the National Climate Assessment, more precipitation has "raised sediments and pollutant concentrations" that could contaminate lakes and make water scarcer.

Harvard University discovered that by 2071, over half of the freshwater basins in the United States may not be able to satisfy their monthly demand, in part because of climate change. The water demand could rise in many places due to higher temperatures and evaporation rates, exacerbating the problem of water scarcity. Millions of people living in India, China, the United States, and South America depend on glaciers as stable water supplies. Glaciers are frozen reservoirs. For the 33rd year in a straight, according to the Global Glacier Monitoring Service, glaciers lost ice volume in 2020. Mauri Pelto, a glacier researcher, said in 2019's State of the Climate that since the 1980s, glacier loss has increased each decade. This occurs in Greenland as a result of both the circulation of warmer air above glaciers and the warmer water below. Especially in Central Asia and the Andes, the IPCC (Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change) predicts that by 2100, a third of the 56 large-scale glacierized catchments will have an average annual run-off of over 10%. There will likely be a 1.5-billion-person impact.

3.0 Impact and Harm of Groundwater Scarcity

The depletion of stored groundwater (falling water levels) and groundwater contamination are the main problems that must be addressed globally to ensure the sustainability of groundwater supplies. Although groundwater will be impacted by climate change, it will be more resilient than surface water because of its natural buffer capacity. Hence, the role of groundwater in the water supply is projected to become increasingly dominant in locations where climate change is anticipated to cause water resources to become scarcer than they are now. One of the key advantages of groundwater systems is their potential as buffers. In general,

it lowers the risk of brief water shortages by allowing extended dry periods to be bridged and generating the circumstances necessary for living in semi-arid and arid locations. A section of the water that has been stored (medium-deep to deep groundwater) becomes considerably less susceptible to abrupt disasters as a result, smoothing out water quality changes and making this fraction ideal as an emergency water source.

3.1 On People

As a result of individuals turning to untreated alternative water sources due to a lack of clean water, diseases including cholera, diarrhoea, and typhoid spread and become more contaminated. In addition to endangering food security and crop output, water shortage also increases the risk of chronic diseases and undernutrition. The international financial cooperative Allianz has conducted research that indicates that several industries, including mining and food and beverage production, are at risk owing to rising water scarcity, which could eventually hinder economic growth. Changes in precipitation and water availability, according to UN-WATER experts, "have been proved to drive refugee dynamics and political instability." Food insecurity and water scarcity are the two risks that low-income populations are most likely to experience. By 2030, water scarcity may force 700 million people to relocate, according to the World Water Institute.

3.2 On Plants

According to research written by Justin Mankin from Columbia University's Lamont-Doherty Earth Observatory, climate change-related water scarcity has a combination of opposing consequences. The efficiency of food production will rise as CO₂ levels rise because photosynthesis will require less water as a result. But when temperatures rise, and growing seasons lengthen, plants in the middle latitudes

absorb more water, leaving less water in streams and soil, leading to high demand for groundwater. According to a study by Imadi et al. (2016), plants with a water shortage reduced photosynthesis and showed indicators of degradation over time.

3.3 Excessive Demand for Crop Yields

Insecticides and fertilizers are used excessively to increase crop yields. Yet if those chemicals are used excessively, the soil and groundwater may get contaminated, which might eventually cause severe water shortages for the community.

3.4 On the Planet

Because it harms entire ecosystems, especially wetlands, water scarcity harms the entire world. Many species not only flourish in wetlands, but they also offer ecological functions like storm protection and water filtration, which are affected by a lack of water. An example of a disturbed ecosystem that has swiftly degraded and diminished is the Aral Sea, which has left behind a habitat that is salty and filthy. Food shortages and a drop in the life expectancy of the local human population were the results of this. Water scarcity will increase with climate change, causing more severe droughts and floods. The security of the water supply for communities and ecosystems downstream will be threatened as glacier loss picks up speed.

4.0 Solutions to Groundwater Scarcity

Groundwater scarcity can be resolved if the following are adhered to;

4.1 Groundwater Sustainability To balance present and future environmental, economic, and social needs, groundwater sustainability is described as the upkeep and protection of

groundwater and related ecosystems (Gordon Groundwater Consultancy, 2011). A relative word, "water scarcity" describes the long-term, unsustainable usage of water resources. To meet present and future beneficial uses of groundwater resources while avoiding unacceptably negative effects on the environment or the economy, groundwater sustainability refers to the development and use of groundwater resources. By ensuring that groundwater is used wisely, supplied, and protected from unfavorable side effects such as land subsidence, saltwater intrusion, depletion of surface water, and degradation of groundwater quality, groundwater sustainability can help solve the problem of water scarcity.

4.2 Groundwater Monitoring

Thus, groundwater needs to be continuously monitored. With improvements in drilling and pumping, the volume of water recovered from groundwater is already greater than that extracted from surface water in many regions of the world. As a result, attitudes toward groundwater are gradually shifting. A crucial component of the hydrologic cycle, groundwater is essential to the survival of practically all ecosystems (Giupponi, 2017). According to Gleeson et al., (2016), there are 22.6 million km³ of groundwater in the top 2 km of the continental crust, of which 0.1 to 5.0 million km³ are younger than 50 years old. The other elements of the active hydrologic cycle pale in comparison to this water supply. Sustainable groundwater management should consider the effects on not only the current generation but also future generations considering the diverse functions and activities of groundwater (Gleeson et al., 2010).

4.3 Technical Methods

Technological approaches including artificial groundwater recharge, water diversion, and effective irrigation have not been able to balance regional groundwater budgets. Other approaches that consider the unique social, economic, political, and environmental conditions of each place are required to supplement these methodologies (AeschbachHertig and Gleeson, 2012).

For instance, in addition to an aquifer's hydrological and hydrogeologic characteristics, regional political, social, and economic factors must be considered to successfully secure or maintain a sustainable groundwater supply (Walton and McLane, 2013). Throughout the past few decades, groundwater research has grown and attracted more attention. This development has been greatly aided by the establishment of multiple academic journals devoted to this subject. This has made it easier to satisfy requests from the industrial and academic sectors. At least in part to the emergence of unexpected or unanticipated difficulties, groundwater research has evolved in both its theme and cross-cutting domains (Wang and Luo, 2020).

4.4 Decision Making

Decision-makers must understand not just the resource itself but also the environment and the potential effects of their management decisions if they are to attain water security for a region. Because of this, a successful planning approach should incorporate risk, social, environmental, and economic analyses (Beek and Arriens, 2014). In other words, the groundwater resource, which serves as a source of freshwater supply, also serves as a sink for leachate, which is produced by human activity close to the wells and originates from the surface. Therefore, it is crucial to take a proactive approach to urban land

use to control or reduce the contamination threat to municipal water wells (Foster and Chilton, 2004; Foster et al., 2011; Foster and Sage, 2017). One strategy that is frequently used in some developed countries is to establish protection areas around a well, but its adoption has proven challenging in Argentina (Massone et al., 2011; Paris et al., 2017; Paoli et al., 2018).

To apply the regulations and controls, pollution sources that are situated inside or close to the perimeters of the protected areas must be identified after they have been designated (using simple or complex approaches). It's crucial to distinguish between point sources and non-point sources during this step.

4.5 Classification of the Mode of Disposal of Potential Contaminants

Notwithstanding its challenges, the distinction between "point source" and "non-point source" for the disposal of possible pollutants has been frequently adopted (Balderacchi et al., 2014). According to section 502 (14) of the Clean Water Act (EPA, 1972), a "point source" is any discernible, confined, and discrete conveyance from which contaminants are or may be discharged. This includes but is not limited to, any pipe, ditch, channel, tunnel, conduit, well, discrete fissure, container, rolling stock, concentrated animal feeding operation, or vessel or other floating craft. Agricultural storm-water discharges and return flows from irrigated fields are not included in this definition.

Some authors, including Foster et al., (2002) and Alberti et al., (2018), also recognize the so-called Multiple Point Sources (MPS), in which the contaminant load originates from several point sources that release a low contaminant mass, are grouped within a relatively large area (for example, an industrial district), and are therefore challenging to identify.

Point pollution sources are more prevalent than non-point ones in metropolitan settings. Some of these point sources produce sewage or effluents that are released into the sewer, close to or inside well-protected regions, via land surfaces, lagoons, tanks, pipes, or other similar structures. In this situation, using a decision support tool to set priorities to safeguard the groundwater supply would be important in addition to defining well-protected zones.

Conclusion

Global warming is a significant factor in the scarcity of freshwater. Our groundwater may be impacted, and water bodies may drain because of increased evaporation of water from rivers and lakes as our average air temperature rises.

Farmers frequently use an excessive amount of fertilizer and pesticides to increase the yield of their crops. Yet if those chemicals are used excessively, the soil and groundwater may get contaminated, which might eventually cause severe water shortages for the community.

Illegal dumping may be a key contributing factor to groundwater shortages. Illegal dumping is still subject to many nations' comparatively lenient rules and enforcement practices. Hence, as it is a simple and affordable method of getting rid of this waste, enterprises routinely dispose of their industrial waste in surrounding exposed land, rivers, and lakes. Nevertheless, this might also result in substantial groundwater pollution, which could make it extremely difficult for people to access water owing to high pollution levels, such as the presence of iron and other dangerous substances that would have seeped into the ground. Our groundwater can become contaminated through soil contamination brought on by agricultural practices or illegal dumping because dangerous elements in the soil

will eventually be flushed into our groundwater during rainfalls.

Locals who depend on pure groundwater for their water supply will consequently experience severe water scarcity, particularly if there is no backup water source in place.

The rate of population growth in the world is worrying. This population rise may be advantageous to some economies, but it also suggests an increase in pollution and waste generation in general. Moreover, consumption will rise overall, which suggests a rise in greenhouse gas emissions, which in turn contributes to the acceleration of global warming. The global population of millions or maybe billions is projected to experience severe water shortages as a result of an increase in the average air temperature.

The degree of water scarcity is significantly influenced by the climate. For example, water shortage is a far bigger issue in countries with consistent rainfall in the Northern hemisphere than in quite hot and arid parts in the Southern hemisphere of our globe. As a result, those who live in hot, dry climate zones will experience water shortages to a far greater extent.

Another important factor contributing to water scarcity may be droughts. Droughts are typical on our globe, particularly in hot, dry areas. Droughts, however, may significantly drop the groundwater level, making it hard for people to access fountains for water. People may experience severe water shortages and negative consequences if these fountains are their only source of water supply.

Bribing officials in corrupt political systems, particularly in nations where corruption is a

serious issue, may also contribute to the local population's lack of access to water. For example, if water is in short supply, residents could have to pay a charge to the government to obtain enough drinking water. Unfortunately, this means that the less wealthy members of the community may not have access to enough water because they simply lack the funds to bribe government officials.

5.2 Recommendation. Groundwater shortage is a serious environmental issue that will get worse because of global warming. Governments from across the world must thus cooperate and find solutions to protect our groundwater from future dangerous repercussions. A liveable future for millions or maybe billions of people globally depend on each of us doing our part to protect the groundwater.

References

- Aeschbach-Hertig, W., & Gleeson, T. (2012). Regional strategies for the accelerating global problem of groundwater depletion. *Nature Geoscience*, 5(12), 853-861.
- Balderacchi, M., Filippini, M., Gemitzi, A., Klöve, B., Petitta, M., Trevisan, M., ... & Gargini, A. (2014). Does groundwater protection in Europe require new EU-wide environmental quality standards? *Frontiers in Chemistry*, 2, 32.
- Besada, H., & Werner, K. (2015). An assessment of the effects of Africa's water crisis on food security and management. *International journal of water resources development*, 31(1), 120-133.

- Bhakar, P., & Singh, A. P. (2018). Life cycle assessment of groundwater supply system in a hyper-arid region of India. *Procedia CIRP*, 69, 603-608.
- Cai, J., Zhao, D., & Varis, O. (2021). Match words with deeds: Curbing water risk with the Sustainable Development Goal 6 index. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 318, 128509.
- Consultancy, G. G. (2011). Sustainable Groundwater Management: Preliminary Approach for Assessing the Sustainability of Groundwater. *CCME Water Management Development Committee*, 48.
- Döll, Petra, Heike Hoffmann-Dobrev, Felix T. Portmann, Stefan Siebert, Annette Eicker, Matthew Rodell, Gil Strassberg, and B. R. Scanlon. "Impact of water withdrawals from groundwater and surface water on continental water storage variations." *Journal of Geodynamics* 59 (2012): 143-156.
- Döll, P. (2009). Vulnerability to the impact of climate change on renewable groundwater resources: a global-scale assessment. *Environmental Research Letters*, 4(3), 035006.
- Foster, S. D., Hirata, R., Ken, W., & Howard, F. (2011). Groundwater use in developing cities: policy issues arising from current trends. *Hydrogeology Journal*, 19(2), 271.
- Foster, S. S. D., & Chilton, P. J. (2004). Downstream of downtown: urban wastewater as groundwater recharge. *Hydrogeology Journal*, 12, 115-120.
- Foster, S., & Sage, R. (2017). Groundwater science in water-utility operations: global reflections on the current status and future needs. *Hydrogeology Journal*, 25(5), 1233.
- Ghori, N. H., Ghori, T., Hayat, M. Q., Imadi, S. R., Gul, A., Altay, V., & Ozturk, M. (2019). Heavy metal stress and responses in plants. *International journal of environmental science and technology*, 16, 1807-1828.
- Giupponi, C., & Gain, A. K. (2017). Integrated spatial assessment of the water, energy, and food dimensions of the sustainable development goals. *Regional Environmental Change*, 17, 1881-1893.
- Gleeson, T., Vandersteen, J., Sophocleous, M. A., Taniguchi, M., Alley, W. M., Allen, D. M., & Zhou, Y. (2010). Groundwater sustainability strategies. *Nature Geoscience*, 3(6), 378-379.
- Haritash, A. K., Gaur, S., & Garg, S. (2016). Assessment of water quality and suitability analysis of River Ganga in Rishikesh, India. *Applied Water Science*, 6, 383-392.
- Jia, X., Hou, D., Wang, L., O'Connor, D., & Luo, J. (2020). The development of groundwater research in the past 40 years: A burgeoning trend in groundwater depletion and sustainable management. *Journal of Hydrology*, 587,

125006.

Margat, J., & Van der Gun, J.

(2013). *Groundwater around the world: a geographic synopsis*. Crc Press.

biomaterials and soils from a Yellowlegged gull (*Larus michahellis*) colony in the Atlantic Islands of Galicia National Park (NW Spain). *Marine pollution bulletin*, 133, 144-149.

Otero, X. L., De La Peña-Lastra, S., Romero, D., Nobrega, G. N., Ferreira, T. O., & PérezAlberti, A. (2018). Trace elements in sanitation, and hygiene. *Comparative Quantification of Health Risks: Global*

Prüss-Üstün, A., Kay, D., Fewtrell, L., & Bartram, J. (2004). Unsafe water,

and Regional Burden of Disease due to Selected Major Risk Factors, 2, 1321-1352.

Rana, R., Ganguly, R., & Gupta, A. K. (2018). Indexing method for assessment of pollution potential of leachate from nonengineered landfill sites and its effect on groundwater quality. *Environmental monitoring and assessment*, 190(1), 46.

Rijsberman, F. R. (2006). Water scarcity: fact or fiction? *Agricultural water management*, 80(1-3), 5-22.

Siddique, Z., Jan, S., Imadi, S. R., Gul, A., & Ahmad, P. (2016). Drought stress and photosynthesis in plants. *Water stress and crop plants: a sustainable approach*, 1, 1-11.

Taylor, R. G., Scanlon, B., Döll, P., Rodell, M., Van Beek, R., Wada, Y., ... & Treidel, H. (2013). Groundwater and climate change. *Nature climate change*, 3(4), 322-329.

Van Beek, E., & Arriens, W. L. (2014). *Water security: Putting the concept into practice*

(p. 55). Stockholm: Global Water Partnership.

Walton, W. C., & McLane, C. F. (2013). Aspects of groundwater supply sustainable yield. *Groundwater*, 51(2), 158-160.

WHO/UNICEF Joint Water Supply, & Sanitation Monitoring Programme. (2014). *Progress on drinking water and sanitation: 2014 update*. World Health Organization.